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Using Indicators to Measure Paddy Farmers' Adaptive Capacity to Climate Change Variability in the Granary Areas of Peninsular Malaysia

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Received Date: 30-Aug-2020

Accepted Date: 15-Oct-2020

Published Date: 30-Apr-2021

Abstract

Sensitivity of paddy rice to climatic perturbation makes paddy farmers to be vulnerable to climate change and variability, this resulted to the decline in paddy productivity and reduction in farmers' income, thereby exacerbating the socio- economic wellbeing and poverty level of the farmers in Malaysia. Tackling vulnerability to climate change through effective policy action requires understanding of farmers' adaptive capacity. This study analysed adaptive capacity of the paddy farmers and factors that causes differences in the farmers' adaptive capacity in the study areas. Paddy farmers' adaptive capacity levels were determined using a composite index score by linearly aggregating the farmers' five capital indicators (human, physical, financial, social, and management capitals). The study showed that adaptive capacity index scores of the entire respondents' ranges from -0.289 to 0.392 with Mean of -0.003 and standard deviation 0.174. About 200 (44.4%) of the respondent have low adaptive capacity, 144 (32.0%) have moderate adaptive capacity, while 106 (23.6%) have high adaptive capacity. Moreover, adaptive capacity as a component of vulnerability has immediate policy implications, in that its improvement reduces the sensitivity levels of the paddy farmers to climate change variability. As such, it is important to evolve national climate change adaptation policy that will guide policy makers to address region specific needs of the paddy farmers. The policy options should involve educating young workforce to embrace paddy farming. More extension services to enhance the skill of the old-aged farmers. Provide access to more financial capital for investment in education etc.

Key Words: Climate change, Variability, Paddy farmers, Adaptive capacity, Indicators

1. Introduction:

The concept of adaptation has a long history and is applied in a multiple of disciplines and its meaning varies relative to a particular field and practice (Moser & Ekstrom 2010). But the concept owe its' origin from evolution in biological science (Grandcolas, 2015). In this context, it refers to "the development of genetic or behavioural characteristics which enable organisms or systems to cope with environmental changes in order to survive and reproduce" (Grandcolas, 2015; Smit & Wandel, 2006). In political ecology, the concept is understood as the relationships between the ecosystems and political economy on the basis of adaptation management of risks as it relates to political and social power, the use of resources and global economy (Sen, 1981; Walker, 2004).

From the standpoint of human- dimension, Adaptation to climate change involves actions taken against a vulnerable system in reaction to real or anticipated climate impulse in order to reduce damage from the changing climatic conditions, including stresses, hazards, or ga in its advantage (Füssel 2007; Rasul &

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Sharma, 2016; Smit, Burton, Klein, & Street, 1999; Smit & Pilifosova, 2003). It can be seen as system's behaviour and characteristic adjustment to deal with external stress (Brooks, 2003).

In the context of climate change, adaptation is viewed as "adjustments in ecological, social cum economic systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli, their effects or impacts" (Begum, Sarkar, Jaafar, & Pereira, 2014; Parry, 2007; Smith, Burton, Klein, & Wandel, 2000). It is also a policy- option in reducing the effects of climate uncertainty (Kurukulauriya & Mendelsohn, 2008). Adaptation involves approaches that integrates given supports that will resolve the causes of vulnerability to efforts that will strictly address impacts of climate change (Begum et al., 2014). It is therefore, closely related with the concepts of vulnerability and adaptive capacity (Adger, Arnell, & Tompkins, 2005; Engle, 2011; Smit & Wandel, 2006). Vulnerability of any system depends on the exposure and sensitivity of the particular system to a precarious or dangerous situations and how the system is capable or is able to adjust, adapt, cope or recover from the shock (Begum et al., 2014; Smit & Wandel, 2006).

While, the interrelationship between environmental and social dynamics determines the exposure and sensitivity of the system, social, economic, cultural and political forces defines the system's capacity to adapt. In the context of climate change, adaptive capacity refers to the system's capacities or potentials to effectively deal with climate variability and change which involves behavioural, resource, and technological changes. It is a prelude to successful planning of adaptation approaches that will lessen the possible huge negative effects arising from climate changes. It therefore allow actors to realize options or benefits from climate changes (Adger et al., 2007; Engle, 2011).

Synonymous to adaptive capacity are concepts like " adaptability, coping ability, management capacity, stability, robustness, flexibility and resilience" (Smit & Wandel, 2006). Usually the underlying factors that influence a system to adapt are the drivers or the determinants of adaptive capacity. This varies with context, spatially and temporally (Adger et al., 2007; Engle, 2011; Smit & Wandel, 2006). At a micro-scale (local level) adaptive capacity is controlled or influenced by some factors of management, financial accessibility, technology and access to information resources, Knowledge (Williams, Fenton, & Huq, 2015), infrastructure, institutions, political control and networks of kinship and so on (Smit & Pilifosova, 2003; Smit & Wandel, 2006). In agricultural crop production, climate change adaptation could be very crucial so long as farmers could be able to counterbalance the anticipated adverse effects of climate change (Kabubo-Mariara & Karanja, 2007). Poor farmers can equally benefit from adaptation to protect their means of sustenance (Bryan, Deressa, Gbetibouo, & Ringler, 2009).

Adaptation measure, particularly anticipatory measures has the propensity to lessen the consequences of climate change on the affected population and facilitate recovery from its impact (Adger et al., 2005). Therefore, in designing precise and successful adaptation policies, it is imperative to understand those factors that account for farmers' adaptation to climate change variability and how to determine them (Below et al., 2012; Bryan et al., 2009; Di Falco, 2014).

In recent times so many conceptual framework have been develop in an effort to advance a general model of vulnerability by describing its components in a comprehensive manner (Fussel, 2007). In spite of the effort to provide generally acceptable guiding principles, many studies could not provide enough explanations to the local adaptation practice particularly as it relates to the smallholder farmers (Below et al., 2012). This study used the approach advanced by Yohe and Tol (2002) and chambers (1988). The approaches gave explanations for the variable nature of farmers' vulnerability, adaptation and adaptive capacities at the micro level of analysis. These two approaches moreover, were extensions on the IPCC Third Assessment Report (Below et al., 2011). The report explained five elements that characterized adaptive capacities of a locality or region, these are technology, economic wealth, infrastructure, institutions and equality and information and skill (Below et al., 2011).

Furthermore, this idea was further expanded to form eight main factors of adaptive capacity to include; presence of wide ranging alternative technology for adaptation, available resources as well as its distribution across the people, the structure of vital institutions, provision of decision making body, as well as the decision

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criteria to be used, human capital stock such as education and personal security, social capital stock that makes property rights more explicit, accessible risk sharing mechanism in a system, information management and determination of credible information by the decision makers, and the public perception of the sources of stress and exposure. These factors also formed valid determinants of adaptation as they affect the ways through which adaptive capacity can be transformed into adaptation (Below et al., 2011).

Although, the factors of adaptive capacity advanced by Yohe and Tol (2002) specifically are adequate to describe local adaptation process, but not specific to a particular sector and could not capture the real situation surrounding smallholder farmers ability to cope with the climate change variability (Below, et al., 2011). Contrarily, arising from numerous case studies of poor smallholder farmers Chambers (1989) came up with his theory of vulnerability and adaptation. Accordingly, Chambers argued that poor individuals normally attempt to reduce their vulnerability not through income maximization but through development and diversification of their capital assets portfolio, he averred that many of the local people do not 'put all their eggs in one basket', they choose to trade-off between their security and income (Chambers, 1989). This analytical framework was further expanded by Scoones (1989) into sustainable livelihoods framework which has become widely use to comprehend the complex nature of local farmers livelihood (Bryan et al., 2015).

Many previous studies were conducted at different scales of analysis ranging from those that used national level data and indicators to understand factors that may cause vulnerability somehow subjectively chosen from the literature (Ericksen et al., 2011). Though, those vulnerability assessment conducted based on theory at national level offer a springing board for more detailed study at micro- level of analysis is desirable. Yet, such national and regional vulnerability assessment to inform policy at the micro-level is still inadequate. This study attempt to replicate micro level vulnerability assessment using indicators theoretically driven, explaining such indicators relationship with vulnerability to climate change variability.

Equally, previous studies in Malaysia were primarily simulation/modelling studies employing process-based modelling approach. The outcome of the previous individual studies described the future or outcome vulnerability of the Malaysian Agriculture. The studies only estimated future impact of climate change on agriculture such as rice productivity and the concomitant welfare loss. The studies do not take into account the current vulnerability vis-à-vis, the role of the existing adaptive capacities in addressing the issues of vulnerability to climate change. For this reason, there is existing gap in climate change vulnerability study more specifically in Malaysia. It is pertinent to have a paradigm shift in the domain of subsequent climate change studies to give more credence to integrated vulnerability assessment of which this existing study intended to achieve.

2. Material and methods.

2.1 *The Study Areas*

The study was conducted in three rice growing areas, IADA, Barat Laut Selangor and Muda Agricultural Development Authority (MADA), Kedah in the west coast and Kemubu Agricultural Development Authority (KADA) Kelantan is located in the east coast of Peninsular Malaysia. The choice of the study areas were primarily based on multi- stage probability sampling.

Barat Laut Selangor (BLS) region (Figure 1) is located in the west coast zone. The climate of this area is characterized by seasonal evenly distributed rainfall. The area has dryness mostly prevailing in the months of February, June and July. The dryness is usually for a short span, lasting for less than one month. This area is also associated with occasional strong draughts of wind and early morning rainfall, particularly within the south west monsoon season starting from May to September. Moreover, the area has soils that are primarily marine and riverine alluvia with medium to heavy textured (Singh, Amartalingam, Wan Harun, & Islam, 1996).

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Figure 1 : Showing IADA, Barat Laut Selangor with the PPK
 (Source: <https://www.google.com/search?q=IADA>)

Barat Laut Selangor is usually considered as the most highly productive rice growing areas in the Peninsular Malaysia, with higher performance more than MADA and KADA. It has an estimated paddy farming households of about ten thousand Two hundred and eighty five paddy farmers in eight Pertubuhan Peladang Kawasan (Area Farmers' Organization).

The Muda Agriculture Development Authority (MADA) is the biggest rice crop area, it covers a total area of 125 555 ha, found in the North- west of Peninsular Malaysia. Out of the total land area, 10,581 ha are in the north- western of Kedah and 20,304 ha are inside the southern part of Perlis state. Nearly 76% of the total area is under paddy cultivation with about 44,306 farming households as at 2015(MADA, 2015). The area is located at about 5°45'–6°30'N latitude and 100°10'–100°30'E longitude in the vast flat alluvial Kedah-Perlis Plain which is 20 km wide and 65 km in length, between the foothills of the Central Range and the Straits of Malacca (Kamaruddin, Ali, & Saad, 2013). This granary area has three administrative regions and 27 district farmers' organizations (Figure 2).

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Figure: 2 : MADA, Kedah showing Administrative Regions and the PPKs (Source: <http://www.mada.gov.my/en/farmer/farmer-institution/profile-map-of-ppk/>)

Kemubu Agriculture Development Authority (KADA), this granary area occupies greater part of the plain of Northern Kelantan; it is an area of high population density. It comprises of 9334 paddy farmers based on the summary of rice incentive list as at 2011 (KADA, 2014). The area comprises of five irrigation sites namely Tumpat comprising of Bunga Raya, and Bakat Baru, Pasir Mas consist of Kubang Sepat, Kubang bunut and Alor Mas, Pasir Puteh consist of Bukit Jawa and Cherang Rotan, Bachok consist of Sri Gunung and Puteri Saadong and Kota Bharu comprises of Nilam Puri, Tanjung Puri, Jaya Peringat and Sg Keterah comprises of Bukit Jawa and Cherang Rotan (Figure 3). The total paddy cultivation area consisting of irrigation infrastructural facilities that aided two planting seasons in a year is about 31,464 hectares.

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Figure 3 : Showing Sampling Areas in KADA

(Source: http://www.kada.gov.my/image/image_gallery?uuid)

2.2 Research Design for the Household Survey

This study employs the use of descriptive correlational design. This is a procedure in quantitative research according to Creswell (2012) a researcher assesses the degree of relationships between a number of variables or to use these relationships in building predictions. Put in another way, correlational studies usually examines so many variables that are believed to be related to a key, complex variable. Data on the farmers' adaptive capacity were obtained through household survey method. This method as rightly posited by Ary, Jacobs, and Sorensen (2010) enables a researcher to gather information from a large sample of people reasonably quicker and less expensive.

2.3 Parameters Selection and Instrument Development

This study used a set of questionnaire in collecting the needed data. The chosen indicators used in the questionnaire captures the biophysical aspects of climate change, the current state of the system exposed to climate change and the socio-economic realities which defines the adaptive capacity of the farmers. The parameters selection to develop the questionnaire were guided by peer- reviewed studies i.e. theory- based (Vincent, 2004) Therefore, this study adopts predefined list approach (Norouzian-Maleki, Bell, Hosseini, & Faizi, 2015) where initial items were obtained from literature review conducted on the quantitative assessment of agricultural vulnerability at the local level to develop the questionnaire. The indicators were combined into the sub- components, based on the specific components of vulnerability as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Compilation of Variables as Determinants of Vulnerability

Components of Vulnerability	Sub-component indicators	Description of Indicators	Functional relation	References
Exposure	Climatic variability	Changes in temperature (minimum & maximum)	+	Piya, et al (2012) Zurovec, et al (2017)
		Changes in precipitation	+	Piya, et al (2012) Wiréhn, et al (2015)
Sensitivity	Income variability	Average annual income	+	Gbetibuou, et al. (2010)
	Yield variability	Average yield of the respondent	+	Montorreso, et al (2014)
	Farm size	Respondents' size of the cultivated land	+	Montorreso, et al (2014) Wiréhn, et al (2015)
	H/H density	Number of people living in a household	+	Dafiesta & Rapera, (2014)
	Health status	Frequency of hospital attendance	+	Berry et al. (2011); Nkondze et al. (2013)
Adaptive Capacity	Human capital	Age of the respondent	-	Antwi Agyei, 2012; Kamaruddin et al. (2013)
		Years of experience in paddy farming	-	Dafiesta & Rapera, (2014) Woldemanuel & Morton (2017)
		Years of education	-	Dafiesta & Rapera, (2014) Kamaruddin et al. (2013)
	Financial Capital	Number of earning families	-	Bellow et al. (2012)
		Land ownership by the respondent	-	Dafiesta & Rapera, 2014
		House owned by the respondent	-	Deininger (2003); Piya et al. (2012)
	Physical capital	Household Savings	-	Montorreso, et al (2014)
		Gross annual income	-	Piya, et al. (2012)
		Accessible road network to the farm	-	Adger et al. (2004); IPCC (2007)
		Condition of the road network	-	Adger et al. (2004)
	Social capital	Distance of irrigation facilities	-	Dafiesta & Rapera(2014)
		Ownership of farm machineries	-	Dafiesta & Rapera(2014)
		Membership in Association/CBO's	-	Dafiesta & Rapera (2014)
		Number of Association Registered	-	Antwi Agyei (2012)
		Attending Associations meeting	-	Deressa et al. (2008)
Existing Adaptation	Access to Extension services	-	Antwi Agyei (2012); Kamaruddin et al. (2013)	
	Receive assistance from the Government	-	Antwi Agyyei (2012)	
	Crop diversification	-	Antwi Agyyei (2012)	
	Use of local indigenous knowledge	-	Ewert et al. (2010)	

Furthermore, the selection of the variables were guided by their analytical soundness, relevance, accessibility and timeliness (Nardo & Saisana, 2008) based on theories that explain the extent and causes of vulnerability. However, such theory-based deductive approaches are identified with some limitations which might lead to prejudice in the process of the indicator selection. The best option is to verify the representativeness of the theory-based indicators with insights gained from focus group discussion (Piya, Maharjan, & Joshi, 2012) conducted at the local level. In this study, this approach was followed after the selection of the indicators, a set of draft questionnaire was developed which was subjected to refinement in a focus group discussion and supplemented the validation of the instrument with expert judgments.

2.4 Instrument Refinement & Validation

Having selected the variables as shown in Table 3.3, a set of questionnaire was drafted using the selected variables comprising of five sections: the farmers' human capital, financial capital, physical capital, social capital and existing adaptation management capital. The draft instrument was subjected to refinement processes such as focus group discussion and further validation through expert opinion.

2.5 Focus Group Discussion

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For the purpose of this study, extension officers working directly under rice division in MADA, who constantly relates with the paddy farmers, were found to be one of the veritable resources to solicit insight and viewpoints that aided the refinement of the questionnaire used in this study. Therefore, a focus group discussion was held with five extension officers working with Rice Division at MADA office, Alor Setar, Kedah on the 22nd October, 2015 between 9.00 am to 11.00 am (2hour session).The researcher facilitated the discussion by briefing the participants on the aim and objectives of the research. The drafted questionnaires were distributed amongst the participants to serve as a guide to the discussion. The participants were first given time to go through the questionnaire individually. The researcher made the group discussion to be task-oriented to enable the review of items in the questionnaire within the timeframe. The researcher asked the participants to listen to each item and to decide whether or not the item is appropriate to be included and whether in their opinion the structured questions could be understood by the local farmers without ambiguity. The participants, as it is normal to focus groups, freely and extensively discussed over several of the items. In few cases, participants swiftly decided upon the unsuitability of some specific items. Equally, participants agreed somewhat expeditiously on the appropriateness of many of the items.

The researcher jotted down the observation raised on each item and the consensus reached on the relevance or otherwise of each item as well as to whether sentences needed to be modified. Example some of the items included to measure financial capital were observed to be bulky and participant suggested lumping some items together and be rewritten. Some items such as “mix- cropping”, “rearing of animals” “lack of extension services” possession of household articles such Television, radio etc. were unanimously found to be inappropriate, other items were agreed to be reworded for better understanding by the respondents who have low level of education. By the end of the discussion, out of the 35 items earlier drafted in the questionnaire, seven were found inappropriate and were removed from the questionnaire leaving behind 28 items. More so, as the questionnaire was administered in Malay language, the participants assisted in editing the language translation. Finally, the researcher refined the instrument based on the input of the focus group. Although, the focus group were planned and conducted primarily for refining the items on the instruments, as well as rewording the wrongly worded questions, the focus groups were further complemented by seeking expert opinion from the academics for further validation of the appropriateness of the instrument items.

2.6 Expert Validation

To confirm the suitability and applicability of the designed instruments specifically on the target population used in this study, panels of two experts were contacted to make the assessment by rating all the items on a 5-point scale (Lynn, 1986).

The result in Table 2 obtained from each Expert scoring was calculated and provides average score for the overall instrument. Therefore, the total instrument ratings were 4.56 (91.2%) and 4.72 (94.5%) for the Expert rating 1 and Expert Rating 2 respectively, with the average inter-rating to be 4.63 (or 93%). This implies that the measuring instrument developed for data collection in this study bears a good content validity (Waltz, Strickland, & Lenz, 2005) and it is suitable and appropriate to be used on the respondents of this study.

Table 2: Average Experts Rating of the Instrument Items

Items in the Instrument	Expert A Rating	Expert B Rating	Mean Rating
Human Capital			
Hcap 2 Age	5	5	5
Hcap 1 Gender of the respondent	5	5	5
Hcap 3 Year of farming experience	5	5	5
Hcap4 Years of education	5	4	4.5
Hcap5 Number of household members with at least primary education	4	5	4.5
Hcap6 Household density	4	5	4.5
Hcap7 Frequency of Hospital attendance	5	4	4.5
Financial Capital			

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Fcap1	Total annual income from Paddy	4	5	4.5
Fcap2	Gross income Annual	5	4	4.5
Fcap3	Total household saving	5	5	5
Fcap4	House ownership	5	5	5
Fcap5	Land ownership	4	5	4.5
Fcap6	Paddy yield	4	5	4.5
Physical Capital		4	4	4
Pcap1	farm walking distance	5	5	4.5
Pcap2	Functional irrigation facilities	5	4	4.5
Pcap3	Accessible road network	4	5	4.5
Pcap4	Condition of the road network	5	5	5
Pcap5	ownership of farm machineries	5	5	5
Social Capital				
Scap1	Membership of Association	5	5	5
Scap2	Number of Association registered by the farmer	4	4	4
Scap3	Frequency of attending association's meeting	5	5	5
Scap4	Access to extension services	5	5	5
Existing Adaptive management Capital				
Mcap1	Receive assistance from the Government	4	5	4.5
Mcap2	Planting of various crops along with Paddy rice	4	4	4
Mcap3	Use of local indigenous knowledge	5	4	4.5
Mcap4	Reliance on friends/family/neighbors in times of crop failure	4	5	4.5
Mcap5	Planting drought resistant variety	5	5	5
Mcap6	Changes in the timing of planting to avoid drought	4	5	4.5
Mcap7	Temporary migration to secure job elsewhere	4	4	4
Mcap8	Rely on income from off- farm jobs	5	5	5
Mcap9	Sell non-farm assets to cope with the effects of climate change	4	5	4.5
Mean Rating Score		4.56	4.72	4.63

2.7 The Study Population and Sample Size

The total population of the paddy rice farmers from the available record shows that there are nearly 300,000 paddy farmers spread in the eight granary areas of the Peninsular Malaysia and 40% of them are full time farmers. Nearly 65% of the total farmers (195,000) are small holders with less than one hectare (DOA, 2008; Man & Ismaila, 2009). The sampling frame for this study was done through multi- stage sampling (Figure 4).

The sample size used in this study was obtained following Israel, (2013) methods of selecting sample size. The method was initially developed by (Yamane, 1967 p886); the methods provide a simplified formula to calculate sample size thus:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where;

n = is the sample size

N = is the population size

e = is the level of precision (5%)

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Figure 4: The Study Sampling Frame

Therefore, from the Yamane's margin of error table at $\pm 5\%$ with a population of nearly 300,000 paddy farmers the required sample size needed is 400. According to the table for determining sample size from a given population proposed by Krejcie and Morgan (1970), the sample size needed for any research with a population of 1000,000 and above is 384. The sample size is calculated using the following formula;

$$s = \frac{X^2 NP(1 - P)}{d^2(N - 1) + X^2 P(1 - P)}$$

Where;

s = Required sample size

X^2 = the table value of chi- square for 1 degree of freedom at the desired confidence level (3.841)

N = the population size

P = the population proportion (assumed to be .50 since this would provide the maximum sample size).

d = the degree of accuracy express as a proportion (.50)

As suggested by some researchers (Israel, 1992; Singh & Masuku, 2013) that a minimum sample size can be increased by 10 to 30 percent to account for inappropriate and incomplete responses in order to achieve the desired statistical power. Similarly, Barlett, Kotrlik, and Higgins (2001) citing Salkind (1977) reported that a researcher can increase the minimum sample size by up to 40% to 50% to accommodate for unreturned and uncooperative respondents. Therefore, going by the rule of thumb that the larger the sample size the better the result, in this study 17.5% was added on the 400 minimum sample size suggested by Krejcie and Morgan (1970) and administered 477 questionnaires on the respondents (Table 3).

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Table 3: Distribution of Survey Sample and Sampling Units

Sampled Granary Areas	Names of the PPK	Farmers Population	Number of Questionnaire Distributed	No. of Respondents Used	%of Sampled Respondents
IADA, BLS (8PPK)	Sungai Nipah	1674	39	36	8
	Panchag Bedana	1996	46	44	9.7
	Sub – Total	3670	85	80	17.7
MADA, Kedah (23 PPK)	Kodiang	1951	48	45	10.0
	Tunjang	1693	42	40	9.0
	Jitra	1199	30	28	6.0
	Hutan Kampog	1383	35	34	8.0
	Alor Senibong	1994	50	47	10.1
	Titi Hajj Idris	1955	49	46	10.2
	Sub – Total	10,175	254	240	53.3
	Total	17,228	477	450	100
KADA, Kelantan (13PPK)	Sungai Ketereh	1248	51	48	11.0
	Sri Gunung	1172	48	45	10.0
	Bunga Raya	963	39	37	8.0
	Sub – Total	3383	138	130	29.0

2.8 Household Survey Questionnaire Structure

A questionnaire instruments were designed and used in collecting primary data on the adaptive capacity of the respondents. The questionnaire consist of five sections, section A measure the human capital dimension of the respondents made up of six items. Information solicited comprises of age of the respondent, years of respondent's experience in paddy farming, respondents,' years of education, number of visits of respondents to hospital and household density of the respondents. Section B is on the financial capital of the respondents which includes information on annual income from paddy and non- paddy, Gross annual income, crop yield variability, landownership, house ownership and the total household saving, Section C comprises of information on respondents physical capital made up of respondents' walking distance from respondents' home to the farm, availability of functional irrigation facilities, accessible road networks in the farm, farm size of the respondents, condition of the road network, and ownership of farm machineries. Section D measures the social capital assets of the respondents including respondents' years of membership in associations/ organization, number of association/organization registered, frequency of respondents attending association/organization's meetings and respondents' access to extension services. Section E consists of existing adaptive management strategies of the respondents, this includes respondents planting various crops along with paddy rice, their use of local indigenous knowledge to cope with adverse effects of climate change and variability, receiving assistance from the government, reliance on remittances from friends, families and/or neighbours in times of crop failure, Planting drought resistant variety, changes in timing of planting to avoid drought occurrences, temporary migration to secure job elsewhere, reliance on income from off-farm jobs and selling of non- farm assets to crop with the effects of climate change and variability. The summary of the items in the questionnaire are provided in Table 4.

Table 4: Questionnaire Sections and items

Questionnaire Sections	No of items
Human Capital	6
Financial Capital	6
Physical Capital	6
Social Capital	4
Existing Adaptive Management Capital	9

2.9 Reliability Test for the Pilot Study

To determine the reliability of the instrument, Cronbach's (alpha) coefficient was used to examine the internal consistency. An overall value of 0.8 were usually reported to be acceptable globally in cognitive test, but Kline (1999) as cited by Field (2014) considered the value of 0.7 as acceptable while using psychological

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constructs due to the variation in the nature of the constructs. The coefficients obtained for the instrument to measure the capital assets of the respondents were adequate as presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Reliability of Pilot Test

S/n	Construct (n=38)	No. Items	Cronbach's alpha
1	Human Capital	6	.790
2	Financial Capital	6	.813
3	Physical Capital	6	.808
4	Social Capital	4	.784
5	Management Capital	9	.824

2.10 Primary Data Collection

The main household survey period spanned for about four months from 25th November, 2015 to 31st March, 2016. Here respondents were selected through systematic random sampling and the questionnaires were self-administered by the households. Six extension officers from each granary area were deployed served as the field assistance who took the responsibility of distribution and retrievals of the questionnaire used. At the end of the survey, out of the 470 questionnaires administered, 450 questionnaires were returned complete with a good response rate of 94.3%. The entire 450 sample were later used in the analysis.

2.11 Development of Adaptive Capacity Assessment Framework Model

Stages or procedures use in developing an index of vulnerability used in the assessment of the respondent climate change vulnerability is provided in the following sub- sections.

Prior to developing adaptive capacity index, all the variables exists in different units of measurement. Therefore, to make the different units and ranges of the different indicators comparable, all the indicators values are normalize before it is aggregated into one composite score. Normalization is the procedure of changing the different indicators to the same standard, by transforming the indicators into pure dimensionless number (Nardo & Saisana, 2008). In this study context, all the indicators of adaptive capacity were standardized using z- score normalization method (Piya et al. 2012; Tesso et al. 2012). The normalization is performed by subtracting the mean from the observed value and divided by the standard deviation for each indicator, thus;

$$\text{Normalized value} = \frac{\text{observed value} - \text{mean}}{\text{Standard Deviation}} = \left(X_{ij} = \frac{X_{1j} - \bar{X}_1}{s_1} \right)$$

where;

\bar{X}_1 is the mean of X_{1j} variable across the different households in region j

s_1 is the standard deviation of the variable X_{1j} .

Then Principal component analysis (PCA) was used to assign weights for the indicators of adaptive capacity following Filmer and Princhett (2001) and Piya et al. (2012). Principal component analysis (PCA) is a method of extracting from a given set of variables those few orthogonal linear combinations of variables that successfully capture the common information. The loadings from the first component of PCA were taken as the weights for the indicators. The weights given for each indicator varies with different signs of the indicators depicting the direction of the relationship with the other indicators used in constructing the respective index. A step-wise PCA was run for the adaptive capacity indicators, the first step PCA was run for each of the asset indicators separately to identify the relative significance of each category of the asset indicators.

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The first Principal component of each of the datasets measuring adaptive capacity were examined. It was discovered that the Kaiser- Meyer- Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy for all the datasets were above 0.5 (ranging from 0.516 to 0.845) which were considered 'great' (Field, 2012). The Bartlett's test of Sphericity ($X^2(36) = 1834.783, P = <.000$) was significant indicating a good correlation between the items for PCA. Lastly, the commonalities of all the items were all above explained 0.47 signifying that the items shared common variance with each other. These indicators proved the suitability of all the data sets to run the PCA. In the second step the index value for each of the assets types was used to run the PCA to examine the relative contribution of each asset category to the adaptive capacity. Then the total capacity index was obtained using the factor loading from the second step PCA for the five asset categories.

2.10 Primary Data Collection

The main household survey period spanned for about four months from 25th November, 2015 to 31st March, 2016. Here respondents were selected through systematic random sampling and the questionnaires were self-administered by the households. Six extension officers from each granary area were deployed served as the field assistance who took the responsibility of distribution and retrievals of the questionnaire used. At the end of the survey, out of the 470 questionnaires administered, 450 questionnaires were returned complete with a good response rate of 94.3%. The entire 450 sample were later used in the analysis.

2.11 Development of Adaptive Capacity Assessment Framework Model

Stages or procedures use in developing an index of vulnerability used in the assessment of the respondent climate change vulnerability is provided in the following sub- sections. Prior to developing adaptive capacity index, all the variables exists in different units of measurement. Therefore, to make the different units and ranges of the different indicators comparable, all the indicators values are normalize before it is aggregated into one composite score. Normalization is the procedure of changing the different indicators to the same standard, by transforming the indicators into pure dimensionless number (Nardo & Saisana, 2008). In this study context, all the indicators of adaptive capacity were standardized using z- score normalization method (Piya et al. 2012; Tesso et al. 2012). The normalization is performed by subtracting the mean from the observed value and divided by the standard deviation for each indicator, thus;

$$\text{Normalized value} = \frac{\text{observed value} - \text{mean}}{\text{Standard Deviation}} = \left(X_{ij} = \frac{X_{1j} - \bar{X}_1}{s_1} \right)$$

where;

\bar{X}_1 is the mean of X_{1j} variable across the different households in region j , s_1 is the standard deviation of the variable X_{1j} .

Then Principal component analysis (PCA) was used to assign weights for the indicators of adaptive capacity following Filmer and Princhett (2001) and Piya et al. (2012). Principal component analysis (PCA) is a method of extracting from a given set of variables those few orthogonal linear combinations of variables that successfully capture the common information. The loadings from the first component of PCA were taken as the weights for the indicators. The weights given for each indicator varies with different signs of the indicators depicting the direction of the relationship with the other indicators used in constructing the respective index. A step-wise PCA was run for the adaptive capacity indicators, the first step PCA was run for each of the asset indicators separately to identify the relative significance of each category of the asset indicators.

The first Principal component of each of the datasets measuring adaptive capacity were examined. It was discovered that the Kaiser- Meyer- Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy for all the datasets were above 0.5 (ranging from 0.516 to 0.845) which were considered 'great' (Field, 2012). The Bartlett's test of Sphericity ($X^2(36) = 1834.783, P = <.000$) was significant indicating a good correlation between the items for PCA.

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Lastly, the commonalities of all the items were all above explained 0.47 signifying that the items shared common variance with each other. These indicators proved the suitability of all the data sets to run the PCA. In the second step the index value for each of the assets types was used to run the PCA to examine the relative contribution of each asset category to the adaptive capacity. Then the total capacity index was obtained using the factor loading from the second step PCA for the five asset categories.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 6: Factor Loading for the First Principal Component Analysis

Adaptive capacity Components	Variables	Factor Loading
Human Capital (.557)	Age of the respondent	.904
	Farmers Years of Experience	.893
	Years of Education	-.508
	Number of people living in a household	.223
	Number of earning families in a Household	.208
Financial Capital (.430)	Landownership	.364
	House ownership	.732
	Gross annual Income	.836
	Total Household Savings	.057
Physical Capital (.610)	Farm walking distance away from home	.624
	Functional irrigation facility	.639
	Accessible road network in the farm	.190
	Condition of the road network in the farm	.788
	Ownership of farm machinery	-.446
Social Capital (.814)	Years of membership of association	.319
	Number of Association registered	-.958
	Frequency of attending meeting in Association	.959
	Access to extension	.918
Existing Adaptation (.703)	Receive assistance from the Government	.764
	Planting of various crops along with Paddy rice	.773
	Use of local indigenous knowledge	.741
	Reliance on friends/family/neighbours' in times of crop failure	.724
	Planting drought resistant variety	.743
	Changes in the timing of planting to avoid drought	.735
	Temporary migration to secure job elsewhere	.708
	Rely on income from off- farm jobs	.693
	Sell non-farm assets to cope with the effects of climate change	.510

Note: All indicators with negative factor loadings signifies that those indicators have little magnitude towards overall weight of the sub-component, component of the index or perhaps the overall index itself.

Table 6 shows the factor loadings obtained from the principal component analysis for the indicators of adaptive capacity across the study areas. Respondents' years of education contribute negatively to their human capital. On the financial capital, gross annual income and house ownership contribute more to the financial capital of the respondents. Condition of road network in the farm and functional irrigation facilities have higher contribution toward the physical capital of the respondents. In terms of social capital the number of association registered by the respondents negatively correlates with their social capital. All variables under existing adaptive management capital strongly contribute to the management capital of the respondents.

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It should be noted that the principal component analysis run for the chosen indicators of adaptive capacity is simply meant for assigning weight, and the weight varies between -1 and +1. The sign either negative or positive denotes the direction of correlation with other indicators used in constructions of the respective index. The degree or magnitude of the weight simply illustrates the relative contribution of each indicator to the value of the index (Piya et al., 2012). Therefore, in this case all indicators with negative values attached to their factor loadings from the PCA implies that those indicators do not contribute substantially to the overall value of the particular sub-component, component of the index or the index itself.

3.1 Respondents' Adaptive Capacity Index

Stepwise factor loadings were obtained to show the relative contribution of each indicator to the sub-components of adaptive capacity (Table 6). The first stage of the principal component analysis illustrates the relative contribution of each indicator for each type of the capital assets. In the second stage PCA indicated the contribution of each capital asset in determining the overall adaptive capacity. Here in developing the index of adaptive capacity aggregate composite index were used, were a single aggregate value of the adaptive capacity index was obtained at the same time transparent composite made-up of the index score was maintained.

The result of the principal component analysis in Table 6 shows that respondents' years of experience have the highest contribution towards their human capital assets. Their age also directly correlate with their farming experience and contributed significantly to their human capital. But respondents' levels of education contributed negatively to their human capital and this could possibly be due to the low level of education among the respondents where only 8% acquired up to tertiary educational level. Both number of adult in a household with at least primary school education and number of earning families have positive but low contributions to the human capital. This is in line with the assumption that the higher the education level the higher the adaptive capacity and the less the vulnerability of the respondent.

For the financial capital assets, gross annual income of the respondent has the highest contribution to the respondents' adaptive capacity followed by the house ownership and then land ownership, while and household savings contribute less to the overall adaptive capacity. For the social capital asset, respondents' belonging to more than one association did not contribute positively to their social capital. But their frequency of attending the association's activity and having access to extension services contributes more to the respondents' social capitals. For the physical assets, accessible road network have the highest contribution followed by the condition of the road network also contributed high, as well as functional irrigation facilities and walking distance to the farm impacts negatively to the adaptive capacity. The respondents' ownership of farm machinery was the least contributing factor to their physical assets. For the existing adaptation management strategies, it was discovered that given assistance to the respondents by the government as well as planting other crops along with paddy has the highest weight. Moreover, the rest of the other factors also contribute significantly to the existing adaptation management strategies.

The result from the second step Principal component analysis indicated that the social capital, management capital and physical capital were the three most important contributors to the aggregate adaptive capacity of the respondents. Human and Financial capitals contributed less to the adaptive capacity of the respondents. The social networks in terms of participation in association, frequent attendance of the association's activity will facilitate access to extension services, these are paramount as illustrated by the high factor loading of the social capital.

Table 7 shows the summary statistics of the weighted scores of the sub-component indicators of adaptive capacity and the aggregate adaptive capacity index score for the respondents in the study areas calculated using equation 3.17 and 3.18 (pg. 149) . The high the mean score, shows the higher the levels of adaptive capacity. The aggregate adaptive capacity index scores of the respondents ranges from -0.289 to 0.392 with a mean adaptive capacity and standard deviation of -0.003 ± 0.174 .

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Table 7: Mean and Standard Deviation of sub- component indicators of Adaptive Capacity

Sub- component Indicators	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	Range
Human Capital	-0.409	0.665	-0.001	0.225	1.073
Financial Capital	-0.198	0.483	0.000	0.113	0.682
Physical capital	-0.726	0.500	-0.001	0.162	1.226
Social Capital	-0.440	0.813	-0.009	0.397	1.253
Adaptive Management Capital	-0.536	0.863	-0.005	0.352	1.400
Aggregate Adaptive Capacity	-0.289	0.392	-0.003	0.174	0.681

Moreover, Table 8 shows the adaptive capacity index scale constructed by dividing the range between the minimum and maximum adaptive capacity scores into three categories of adaptive capacity; thus from -0.269 to -0.085 as less adaptive capacity; a score of -0.063 to 0.164 is considered moderate adaptive capacity and 0.165 and above, as high adaptive capacity.

Table 8: Adaptive Capacity Index Scale

Scale	Description
-0.289 to -0.062	Low Adaptive Capacity
-0.063 to 0.164	Moderate Adaptive Capacity
0.165 and above	High Adaptive Capacity

3.2 Assessment of the Respondents' Level of Adaptive Capacity

Using the scale above the adaptive capacity levels of the individual respondents were assessed. Table 9 show the summary statistics of the individual respondents' adaptive capacity index scores. The adaptive capacity index scores of the entire respondents' ranges from -0.289 to 0.392 with Mean of -0.003 and standard deviation 0.174. About 200 (44.4%) of the respondent have low adaptive capacity, 144 (32.0%) have moderate adaptive capacity, while 106 (23.6%) were found to have high adaptive capacity.

Table 9: Respondents' Levels of Adaptive Capacity

Category	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Less Adaptive capacity	200	44.4
Moderate adaptive capacity	144	32.0
High adaptive capacity	106	23.6

Table 10 present the scores of each component and total adaptive capacity Index of the respective twelve PPKs in the study areas. From the result in Table 10 Sungai Nipah relatively appeared to have the highest Adaptive capacity score due to its higher scores in physical, social and existing adaptation management capitals and very low in human and financial capital. Bunga Raya fares the best in the two of the capital assets (human and social) and second best in human capital and the respondents' existing adaptation management strategies, and it is the second best in the total adaptive capacity. Penchang Bedana fares well in the management capital and the second best in terms of physical capital but it is rated low in terms of human and financial capitals and therefore, it is ranked the third in aggregate adaptive capacity index. In MADA, Kedah, all the PPK's have a weak and negative scores in all the five capital assets except for Alor Senibong which has the best in the human capital and third highest score in terms of financial assets. Furthermore, three PPKs with the lowest adaptive capacity, viz; Tunjang, Hutan Kampong and Jitra were all found in MADA granary area in Kedah.

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Table 10: Aggregate Adaptive Capacities for the Study PPKs

Granary	PPK	H. Capital	F. Capital	P. Capital	Social Capital	Management Capital	Aggregate Adaptive Capacity	Rank
IADA	Sungai Nipah	0.079	0.036	0.13	0.461	0.175	0.176	1
	Penchang Bedana	-0.036	-0.03	0.132	0.216	0.374	0.131	3
	TOTAL	0.015	-0.0002	0.131	0.326	0.284	0.151	1
MADA	Kodiang	-0.101	-0.055	-0.067	-0.311	-0.136	-0.134	8
	Tunjang	-0.104	-0.075	-0.066	-0.335	-0.273	-0.171	11
	Jitra	-0.108	-0.082	-0.091	-0.313	-0.197	-0.158	9
	Hutan Kampong	-0.092	-0.086	-0.068	-0.351	-0.206	-0.161	10
	Aloe Senibong	0.151	0.04	-0.061	-0.28	-0.214	-0.073	6
	Titi Hajj Idris	-0.102	0.042	-0.04	-0.323	-0.106	-0.106	7
	TOTAL	-0.052	-0.029	-0.063	-0.317	-0.186	-0.129	3
KADA	Sungai Ketereh	0.042	0.078	-0.007	0.264	0.218	0.119	5
	Sri Gunung	0.113	0.023	0.03	0.345	0.111	0.125	4
	Bunga Raya	0.096	0.058	0.084	0.501	0.115	0.171	2
	TOTAL	0.082	0.053	0.032	0.36	0.151	0.136	2

In addition, aggregating the component of adaptive capacity at the granary level as presented in Figure 5 allows for inter comparability between the granary areas which gives entirely a new picture of the adaptive capacity. Based on the aggregate score, IADA, BLS granary area has the highest score in the total adaptive capacity index. The granary has the highest score in two capitals (physical, and management capitals) and second highest score in terms of human and financial capitals. While KADA, Kelantan has the second highest aggregate adaptive capacity index score, where it has the highest score in social capital and human capitals, and second highest in physical capital and adaptive management practices. The last in the ranking of the adaptive capacity index score is MADA, Kedah where it has the lowest scores in all the components of the adaptive capacity.

Figure 5 : Aggregate Adaptive Capacity Index at the Granary Level

4. Conclusions & Recommendations

This study illustrated the features associated with the adaptive Capacity of the Paddy farming households in Peninsular Malaysia. First, this study showed that adaptive capacity as a component of vulnerability to climate changes has spatial characterization across the granary areas in Malaysia. Furthermore, it was observed that there were differences in adaptive capacity between the three granary areas. Moreover, adaptive capacity as a component of vulnerability has immediate policy implications. Improvement on the adaptive capacity by implications affects the sensitivity levels of the paddy farming community.

Therefore, this study recommends the need for national climate change adaptation policy that will guide policy makers to address region specific needs of the paddy farming households. The low contribution of human capital to the adaptive capacity of the respondents necessitates a policy option for government to focus on educating the young workforce amongst the paddy farming households to be engaged into the paddy farming. While existing respondent who are old aged, their skills can further be developed through the existing effort of the extension services.

The financial capital among the respondent is so low, thus this has a number of adverse effect in their livelihood. Financial capital will enable the farming household to make investment in education; their savings can be used as capital for investment. Therefore there is the need to increase their access to financial capital.

Considering the importance of adaptive capacity in mitigating vulnerability to climate change, policy should focus on MADA granary area to build on the existing adaptive capacity. As all the components of adaptive capacity in this area are so low despite it is the largest granary with highest population of paddy respondent. To build on their adaptive capacity, the social capital of the respondent in terms their engagement and active participation in all activities related to farmers' organization need to be emphasized, hence farmers association has a role to play in this direction. The social networks in terms of participation in association, frequent attendance of the associations' activity will facilitate access to extension services.

Developing respondents' human capital in areas of education should be improved and active participation of younger generation in paddy farming should be encouraged. Other aspects such as the financial capital of the respondent, physical capital as well as their existing adaptive management practices needs to be improved in this granary area. This will help to build the respondent adaptive capacity and enhance their resilience which will mitigate their vulnerability to climate changes.

Authors' Contributions

DYG, conceived the idea, designed the framework and wrote the manuscript; AMA, participated in the design of the study and helped in organizing and writing of the manuscript, and AA, assisted in the analysis of the data.

Funding:

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Conflict of Interests:

The authors wish to summarily declare that they have no conflict of interest concerning the publication of this paper.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their gratitude to the Staff and management of Integrated Agricultural Development Authority (IADA), Barat Laut Selangor and Muda Agricultural Development Authority (MADA),

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Kedah and Kemubu Agricultural Development Authority (KADA), Kelantan for giving us the permission to conduct this research in their granary areas.

References

- i Adger, N. W., Arnell, N. W., and Tompkins, E. L. 2005. *Successful adaptation to climate change across scales. Global Environmental Change*, 15(2), 77-86.
- ii Adger, W. N., Agrawala, S., Mirza, M. M. Q., Conde, C., O'Brien, K., Pulhin, J., . . . Takahashi, K. 2007. *Assessment of adaptation practices, options, constraints and capacity. Climate change*, 717-743.
- iii Ary, D., Jacobs, L. C., and Sorensen, C. 2010. *Introduction to research in education. Australia: Wardsworth.*
- iv Barlett, J. E., Kotrlik, J. W., and Higgins, C. C. 2001. *Organizational research: Determining appropriate sample size in survey research. Information technology, learning, and performance journal*, 19(1), 43.
- v Begum, R. A., Sarkar, M. S. K., Jaafar, A. H., and Pereira, J. J. 2014. *Toward conceptual frameworks for linking disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation. International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 10, Part A(0), 362-373. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2014.10.011>
- vi Below, T. B., Mutabazi, K. D., Kirschke, D., Franke, C., Sieber, S., Siebert, R., and Tscherning, K. 2012. *Can farmers' adaptation to climate change be explained by socio-economic household-level variables? Global Environmental Change*, 22(1), 223-235.
- vii Brooks, N. 2003. *Vulnerability, risk and adaptation: A conceptual framework. Tyndall Centre for Climate Change Research Working Paper*, 38, 1-16.
- viii Bryan, B. A., Huai, J., Connor, J., Gao, L., King, D., Kandulu, J., and Zhao, G. 2015. *What actually confers adaptive capacity? Insights from agro-climatic vulnerability of Australian wheat. PloS one*, 10(2).
- ix Bryan, E., Deressa, T. T., Gbetibouo, G. A., and Ringler, C. 2009. *Adaptation to climate change in Ethiopia and South Africa: options and constraints. environmental science & policy*, 12(4), 413-426.
- x Creswell, J. W. 2012. *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative (Fourth Edition ed.)*. Boylston street, Boston, USA: Pearson Education, Inv.
- xi Di Falco, S. 2014. *Adaptation to climate change in Sub-Saharan agriculture: assessing the evidence and rethinking the drivers. European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 41(3), 405-430. doi:10.1093/erae/jbu014
- xii DOA. 2008. *Statistical Handbook. Malaysia: Ministry of Agriculture.*
- xiii Engle, N. L. 2011. *Adaptive capacity and its assessment. Global Environmental Change*, 21(2), 647-656.
- xiv Füssel, H. 2007. *Vulnerability: a generally applicable conceptual framework for climate change research. Global Environmental Change*, 17(2), 155-167.
- xv Grandcolas, P. 2015. *Adaptation. In T. Heams, P. Huneman, G. Lecointre, & M. Silberstein (Eds.), Handbook of Evolutionary Thinking in the Sciences (pp. 77-93). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands.*
- xvi Israel, G. D. 1992. *Determining sample size: University of Florida Cooperative Extension Service, Institute of Food and Agriculture Sciences, EDIS Gainesville.*
- xvii Kabubo-Mariara, J., and Karanja, F. K. 2007. *The economic impact of climate change on Kenyan crop agriculture: A Ricardian approach. Global and Planetary Change*, 57(3), 319-330.
- xviii Kamaruddin, R., Ali, J., and Saad, N. M. 2013. *Happiness and its Influencing Factors among Paddy Farmers in Granary Area of Mada. World Applied Sciences Journal*, 28(EFMO)), 91-99.
- xix Kurukulasuriya, P., and Mendelsohn, R. O. 2008. *A Ricardian analysis of the impact of climate change on African cropland. African Journal of Agriculture and Resource Economics*, 2(1).
- xx Lynn, M. R. 1986. *Determination and quantification of content validity. Nursing research*, 35(6), 382-386.

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- xxi Man, N., and Ismaila, S. S. 2009. *Off-farm employment participation among paddy farmers in the Muda Agricultural Development Authority and Kemasin Semerak granary areas of Malaysia. Asia-Pacific Development Journal*, 16(2), 141-153.
- xxii Moser, S. C., and Ekstrom, J. A. 2010. *A framework to diagnose barriers to climate change adaptation. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107(51), 22026-22031.
- xxiii Nardo, M., and Saisana, M. 2008. *OECD/JRC handbook on constructing composite indicators. Putting theory into practice: Paris: OECD Publishing.*
- xxiv Norouzi-Maleki, S., Bell, S., Hosseini, S.-B., and Faizi, M. 2015. *Developing and testing a framework for the assessment of neighbourhood liveability in two contrasting countries: Iran and Estonia. Ecological indicators*, 48, 263-271.
- xxv Parry, M. L. 2007. *Climate Change 2007: impacts, adaptation and vulnerability: contribution of Working Group II to the fourth assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (Vol. 4): Cambridge University Press.*
- xxvi Piya, L., Maharjan, K. L., and Joshi, N. P. 2012. *Vulnerability of rural households to climate change and extremes: Analysis of Chepang households in the Mid-Hills of Nepal. Paper presented at the 2012 Conference, August 18-24, 2012, Foz do Iguacu, Brazil.*
- xxvii Rasul, G., and Sharma, B. 2016. *The nexus approach to water–energy–food security: an option for adaptation to climate change. Climate Policy*, 16(6), 682-702.
- xxviii Salkind, N. j. (Ed.) 1977. *Exploring Research (3rd ed.)*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- xxix Sen, A. 1981. *Poverty and famines: an essay on entitlement and deprivation: Oxford university press.*
- xxx Singh, A. S and Masuku, M. B. (2013). *Fundamental of applied research and sampling techniques. Int J Med Appl Sci*, 2(4), 123-124.
- xxxi Singh, S., Amartalingam, R., Wan Harun, W., and Islam, M. 1996. *Simulated impact of climate change on rice production in Peninsular Malaysia. Paper presented at the Proceeding of National Conference on Climate Change.*
- xxxii Smit, B., Burton, I., Klein, R. J., and Street, R. 1999). *The science of adaptation: a framework for assessment. Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 4(3-4), 199-213.
- xxxiii Smit, B., and Pilifosova, O. 2003. *Adaptation to climate change in the context of sustainable development and equity. Sustainable Development*, 8(9), 9.
- xxxiv Smit, B., and Wandel, J. 2006. *Adaptation, adaptive capacity and vulnerability. Global Environmental Change*, 16(3), 282-292.
- xxxv Smith, B., Burton, I., Klein, R. J., and Wandel, J. 2000. *An anatomy of adaptation to climate change and variability. Climatic change*, 45(1), 223-251.
- xxxvi Walker, R. 2004. *Social Security And Welfare: Concepts And Comparisons: Concepts and Comparisons: McGraw-Hill Education (UK).*
- xxxvii Waltz, C. F., Strickland, O.L., and Lenz, E. R. 2005. *Content Analysis. Measurement in nursing and health research*, 3, 239-245.
- xxxviii Williams, C., Fenton, A., and Huq, S. 2015. *Knowledge and adaptive capacity. Nature Climate Change*, 5(2), 82-83.